

Contemporary Neo-Confucianism 當代新儒家

also known as “New Confucianism”, “Modern Confucianism”

By King Pong Chiu, New Asia Institute of Advanced Chinese Studies

Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Neo-Confucian Traditions, Religious Group, Contemporary Neo-Confucianism, Chinese Religion, Confucianism

The ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ is a philosophical thought or a philosophical school that it develops the ideas based on a re-interpretation of traditional Confucianism, in order to make Confucianism more relevant to the needs of the modern world. Mainly developed by some thinkers who escaped from the mainland China to Hong Kong and Taiwan in 1949, ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ began to be influential in the academia in Hong Kong and Taiwan since late 1950s, and finally affected the Confucian studies in mainland China since 1980s. The term ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ is, in fact, firstly suggested and promoted by the scholars in mainland China at that time. Theoretically, the group of ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ could include any scholars who share the same ideal of re-interpreting Confucianism in Hong Kong, Taiwan and mainland China, the term practically refers to those who develops their thoughts in Hong Kong and Taiwan, as the re-interpretation of traditional Confucianism varies hugely between the scholars in these two places and the mainland. In general, the ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ in Hong Kong and Taiwan regards Confucianism the mainstream intellectual tradition in the Chinese society, and any modernization of China and the Chinese society needs to consider the pros and cons of this tradition. It is based on Confucianism that Chinese people develop its model of modernization while it is also the same intellectual tradition that it may hinder Chinese society from progressing. Under such considerations, several important issues are to be handled: the relationship between Confucianism and democracy as well as science; the relationship between Confucianism and Western philosophy; and the relationship between Confucianism and other traditional Chinese thought such as Buddhism and Taoism. In general, ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ considers that Confucianism could not only co-exist with other Chinese traditions, democracy, science and Western philosophy, but even improve the quality of them. On the one hand, ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ seems progressive as it does not put Confucianism into a contradictory position with such modern values as democracy and science. On the other hand, however, it is considered conservative as it seems to hold a position that, in a sense, Confucianism is more important than the values as mentioned above. The ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ in Hong Kong and Taiwan involves some important figures, such as Xiong Shili (熊十力, 1885 – 1968), Carsun Chang (張君勱, 1887 – 1969), Liang Shuming (梁漱溟, 1893 – 1988), Ch’ien Mu (錢穆, 1895 – 1990), Thomé H. Fang (方東美, 1899 – 1977), Xu Fuguan (徐復觀, 1904 – 1982), Tang Junyi (唐君毅, 1909 – 1978) and Mou Zongsan (牟宗三, 1909 – 1995). However, as the approaches employed to re-interpret Confucianism differ among them, their conclusions towards the relationships between Confucianism and the issues as mentioned above are also various. To a large extent, the term ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ simplifies the complexities of the thoughts of these thinkers, and the rationale behind using the term is in doubt in some ways. To make the situation more complicated, some scholars in Confucianism from the present mainland China, Jiang Qing (蔣慶, 1953 – present) for example, challenge the usage of the term, claiming that mainland China has her own perspective of re-interpreting traditional Confucianism and this perspective is different from those in Hong Kong and Taiwan. To the scholars from the mainland, Confucianism is the essence of Chinese culture and it is not correct to think of its relationship with those issues coming from the West, such as democracy and science. This kind of interpretation of Confucianism is considered highly conservative though it is rather popular in the academia of mainland China. Due to the diversity of interpretation, the term ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ never has a rigid definition. Despite its popularity, ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’ is mainly a target of discussion in academia rather than a

religious or philosophical group with influence in society.

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Beijing, Shanghai, Hong Kong, and Taiwan

Region tags: Asia, Taiwan, East Asia, China, Hong Kong Special Administration Region

Areas of importance for Contemporary Neo-Confucianism

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: John Makeham ed., *New Confucianism: A Critical Examination* (New York: Palgrave MacMillan, 2003).
- Source 2: John Makeham, *Lost Soul: Confucianism in Contemporary Chinese Academic Discourse* (Cambridge MA.: Harvard University Asia Center, 2008).
- Source 3: Sor-hoon Tan, 'Contemporary Neo-Confucian Philosophy'. In Bo Mou ed., *History of Chinese Philosophy* (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), pp. 539-608.
- Source 1: Shu-hsien Liu, 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism: Its Background, Varieties, Emergence, and Significance'. *Dao: A Journal of Comparative Philosophy* vol.2, no. 2 (2003): 213-233.
- Source 2: Jana S. Rošker, *The Rebirth of the Moral Self: The Second Generation of Modern Confucians and their Modernization Discourses* (Hong Kong: The Chinese University Press, 2016).
- Source 3: Jiang Qing, Edmund Ryden trans., Daniel A. Bell and Fan Ruiping ed., *A Confucian Constitutional Order: How China's Ancient Past Can Shape Its Political Future* (Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2013)..
- Source 1: 方克立、李錦全編，《現代新儒家學案》(北京：中國社會科學出版社，1995年)。
- Source 2: 吳汝鈞，《當代新儒學的深層反思與對話詮釋》(台北：台灣學生書局，2009年)。

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: n/a

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: n/a

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: As many figures related to the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' used Buddhist ideas to develop their thoughts, the relationship between 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' and Buddhism is always debatable. Individual figures, Xiong Shili for example, was regarded as a betrayer of Buddhism by some Buddhist scholars in his time, as Xiong firstly learned Buddhism but later changed his attention to Confucianism and blamed Buddhism in return. Tang Junyi was also criticized that he used Buddhist ideas to explain Confucianism and therefore his thought is a kind of confusion of ideas. For details, see John Makeham ed., *Transforming Consciousness: Yogācāra Thought in Modern China* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014). Also see King Pong Chiu, Thomé H. Fang, Tang Junyi and *Huayan Thought: A Confucian Appropriation of Buddhist Ideas in Response to Scientism in Twentieth-Century China* (Leiden: Brill, 2016).

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: For some figures in the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', Confucianism and Buddhism not only could co-exist but the latter helped improve the shortcomings of the former. For example, Tang Junyi considered that the Buddhist theory of doctrinal classification is essential to modern Confucianism, as the theory, on the one hand, stresses the strengths of different ideas while, on the other hand, considers that these strengths of different ideas are only reasonable from certain perspectives. In short, there is no absolute truth that it could apply to all situations. Confucianism, in this sense, is only applicable to individuals in certain situations. To Tang, this openness is exactly what present Confucianism needs. For details, see King Pong Chiu, Thomé H. Fang, Tang Junyi and *Huayan Thought: A Confucian Appropriation of Buddhist Ideas in Response to Scientism in Twentieth-Century China* (Leiden: Brill, 2016).

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: There are always their intentions for the thinkers in the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' to borrow ideas from Buddhism. The interaction between 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' and Buddhism, therefore, is not neutral but intentional.

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: The dispute between 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' and Buddhism is only restricted to a theoretical level. No case of violence between two groups is recorded.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– I don't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The identity of a Confucian is always rather debatable in modern Chinese society, as there is no official organization who has the right or reputation to identify a Confucian, not to mention assigning religious affiliation. In a sense, Confucianism nowadays is a kind of personal quality rather than a formal identity. For details, see Xinzhong Yao, 'Who is a Confucian Today? A critical reflection on the issues concerning Confucian identity in modern times', *Journal of Contemporary Religion* vol. 16, no. 3 (2001): 313-328.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: On the one hand, anyone who shares the ideal of making Confucianism survive and even revive in modern days could consider him or herself a member of the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. On the other hand, however, some scholars tend to consider that the membership or identity are only for those who have studied under the figures of the 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. In this sense, the so-called membership of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' is very open while at the same time rather exclusive. And there is no strict process to recruit new members and being a member of the group is somehow arbitrary.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: For the 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' in Hong Kong and Taiwan, no clear official political support is observed. For the so-called 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' in mainland China, however, some of them seems to be supported and even promoted by the officials. For details, see 蔣慶、陳明等著，任重編，《中國必須再儒化：「大陸新儒家」新主張》(新加坡：八方文化，2016年)。

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since the membership or identity of the group is rather arbitrary, there is no clear conception of apostasy in the group.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As the identity of a Confucian is always in doubt in modern times, the number of adherents is largely unknown. In short, the identity and number of Confucian nowadays, including those named as the member of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' is highly controversial.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' is a part of Confucianism, though the thinkers in the group mainly consider Confucianism a philosophy rather than a religion.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of the academic achievement and personal charisma, Tang Junyi and Mou Zongsan are unanimously considered the leaders of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. Since Mou was a student of Xiong Shili, Xiong is considered the master of the group by individual scholars.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: As the leaders are actually some scholars, their views are always under reviewed and assessed. In principle, it is normal to point out their shortcomings, though in reality it is not commonly seen as the leaders are highly respected by their students and followers.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: There are some very important books or essays which, to some extent, could be considered 'scripture' in the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. There are some examples: Xiong Shili's A New Treatise on Consciousness-only (新唯識論) Tang Junyi's The Existence of Life and Horizons of Mind (生命存在與心靈境界) Mou Zongsan's Treatise on Summum Bonum (圓善論) Tang Junyi, Carsun Chang, Mou Zongsan and Xu Fuguan's 'A Manifesto on [the] Reappraisal of Chinese Culture - Our Joint Understanding of the Sinological Study Relating to 'the' World Cultural Outlook' (中國文化與世界：我們對中國學術研究及中國文化與世界文化前途之共同認識), a long essay or a joint declaration published in 1958

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: In principle, the "scriptures" are open for re-interpretation, though in reality, most of the re-interpretations as seen so far tend to follow, if not repeat, what the text said.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Both the New Asia College, now a part of The Chinese University of Hong Kong, and the New Asia Institute of Advanced Chinese Studies, are considered sacred by some of those who are interested in Contemporary Neo-Confucianism, as the college and the institute were found by some important figures of the group, such as Ch'ien Mu and Tang Junyi, and other influential figures of the group like Mou Zongsan and Xu Fuguan were also teaching there.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the definition of 'spirit'. For those in the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', 'spirit' means mental activities with moral value. Since such activities are not controlled by body, there is a spirit-body distinction in the thought of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. In fact, one of the main concerns of the thought is to encourage humans to enhance their 'spirit' but not restrict themselves to the desires of body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on individuals. Figures belonged to the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' seem no different from general public among Chinese people in this regard.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: The goods, if there are any, mainly represent that the dead is to be missed but not forgot by others, so that the dead is still 'living' in the heart of others. It is probably the main characteristic of the idea of 'spirit' as understood by the figures in 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'.

↳ Valuable items:

– I don't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: It depends on individuals. Figures belonged to the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' seem no different from general public among Chinese people in this regard.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The understanding of 'supernatural beings' in Contemporary Neo-Confucianism may be different from that of many religions. Although the former considers that there is 'spirit' existing beyond the body, this 'spirit' is not equal to a soul but a kind of spiritual or mental activities that a person shows to others, such as wishes, perseverance and even emotion. Such activities can be 'felt' by other people, so that the latter can communicate with those showing the 'spirit' through this 'feeling'. Furthermore, a 'supernatural being', as most of the figures of Contemporary Neo-Confucianism understands, could be a universe full of moral values or virtues. These values or virtues can only be comprehended by those who live their lives morally. In short, people with morality could see the universe in a moral way and as a result the universe will also be full of moral values or virtues. The existence of a 'supernatural being', in this sense, depends on the quality or standard of cultivation of the observer. In short, a person needs to improve him or herself in order to comprehend the existence of such a 'supernatural being'.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: If 'spirit' here means 'soul', the answer is no. If the 'spirit' means the 'spirit activities' as mentioned previously, the answer is yes.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: In 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', the 'communication' between the 'spirit' of the dead and the living means the 'spirit activities' of the dead are to be remembered or felt by the living, and the living is affected by the memories or feeling related to the dead.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: For the figures in the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', humans can develop certain kinds of 'divinity', such as manifesting the values of morality and beauty, which are not observed explicitly in other animals other than humans, though these values may not be necessarily considered 'divinity' in other religions.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams:
 - No
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' believes that the fate of the world depends on the quality of humans. In order to change the world into a better place, one needs to improve the quality of him or herself, and try to extend this quality to help others to improve themselves. The ultimate aim of such improvement is to save the world from different misfortunes so that the entire humans can eventually live a better life. In this sense, both Messianism or Eschatology depend on the choice of human beings, but not a 'supernatural being' beyond humans.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Since 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' developed during the times around the Second World War and Cold War, the thinkers always considered that it was crucial for humans to improve or the world would be in great trouble.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Since 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' believes that the fate of the world depends on the quality of humans, that means as long as humans improve themselves the world can then be saved, people who are eager to improve should survive the eschaton in principle.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The act of humans depends on situations, and there is no universal social norm that one needs to follow anyway. However, 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' considers that all of the act needs to meet one's conscience or the value of humaneness (or Ren 仁 in Confucian term). In this regard, humaneness or Ren could be considered the general social norm one needs to follow, though the interpretation of Ren is always open but not rigid, depending on the situation individual faces.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: In 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', moral values are manifested in one's daily living. Therefore, there is no clear conventional vs. moral distinction in the thought.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The act of humans depends on situations, but all acts need to meet one's conscience or the value of humaneness (or Ren 仁 in Confucian term). In this regard, humaneness or Ren is the centrally important virtue advocated by the group.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– No

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– No

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– No

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The act of humans depends on situations, but all acts need to meet one's conscience or the value of humaneness (or Ren 仁 in Confucian term). In this regard, humaneness or Ren is the centrally important virtue advocated by the group. In general, virtues which are not against humaneness or Ren are advocated by the group.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: As the members of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' are not required to sacrifice anything, it is criticized by some scholars that the thought becomes a kind of conceptual game, but fails to help ones to transform or improve themselves. For details, see 鄭家棟, 《當代新儒學論衡》(台北: 桂冠圖書公司, 1995年)。Also see 林鎮國, 《辯證的行旅》(台北: 立緒文化, 2002年)。

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: The act of humans depends on situations, and there is no universal social norm that one needs to follow anyway. However, 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' considers that all of the act needs to meet one's conscience or the value of humaneness (or Ren 仁 in Confucian term). In this regard, humaneness or Ren could be considered the general social norm one needs to follow, though the interpretation of Ren is always open but not rigid, depending on the situation individual faces.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Worshipping the ancestors and Confucius is important to the members of the group, though it is not a must for them to attend the worship ceremony. Attending the ceremony is totally spontaneous.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Normally twice per year, one in spring and one in autumn.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Worshipping Confucius is important to some of the members of the group, though it is not a must for them to attend the worship ceremony. Worship ceremony could be large-scale but attending the ceremony is totally spontaneous. To them, one's attitude towards Confucius is more important than the ritual.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' is mainly a group of scholars who share the same faith in Confucianism. In short, it is a group without strict organization. The society to which it belongs is, in this sense, really weak.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Notes: Perhaps individuals in the group have interaction with a formal bureaucracy within their group, but the nature of interaction seems private but not open.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No